

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF GLIMEPIRIDE IN PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM BY UV VISIBLE SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD

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Abstract:

Glimiperide is an anti-diabetic drug which is used for the treatment of diabetes. In present work, a simple, sensitive, accurate and economical spectroscopic method has been developed for the estimation of glimepiride in bulk and in pharmaceutical dosage forms.

An absorption maximum was found to be at 249 nm with the solvent system of chloroform. The drug follows Beer's law limits in the range of 5-30 µg/ml with correlation coefficient of 0.999732. Results of the analysis were validated for accuracy, precision, LOD. LOD were found to be satisfactory. The linearity study for Glimepiride was found in concentration range of 5µg-25µg and correlation coefficient (r) was found to be 0.999 and Regression coefficient (r²) 0.999. %Recovery studies were carried out and the percentage recovery was found to be in the range of 100.8% - 101%. %RSD of Absorbance for Intraday, Inter day precision was 1 and 0.95, % RSD for Ruggedness was found to be less than 2. LOD and LOQ of calibration curve of drug prepared in 0.1N NaOH were found to be 0.5 and 1.5 µg/ml, respectively. The proposed method is simple, rapid and suitable for the routine quality control analysis.

Key words: Glimepiride, Tablets, UV spectrophotometry.

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Please cite this article in press K.Srivani et al., *Method Development And Validation Of Glimepiride In Pharmaceutical Dosage Form By UV Visible Spectrophotometric Method.., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12(07).*

INTRODUCTION:

Glimepiride i.e. 1-[[4-[2-(3-Ethyl-4-methyl-2-oxo-3-pyrroline-1-carboxamido)-ethyl] phenyl] sulphonyl]-3- trans-(4-methylcyclohexyl) urea is a hypoglycemic agent belonging to the second generation sulfonylurea's.¹ It appears to lower blood glucose by stimulating insulin release from beta cells in the pancreatic islets possibly due to increased intracellular Camp.² The aim of present work is to develop and validate a simple UV spectrophotometric method to be applied for the quantification of Glimepiride in Pharmaceutical dosage form, which serves as a tool for the quality control of pharmaceutical dosage forms³

Figure 1 Structure of GLImipiride

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Apparatus

A Shimadzu model 1800 double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer with spectral width of 1 nm, wavelength accuracy of ± 0.1 nm and a pair of 10 mm matched quartz cell was used to measure absorbance of all the solutions. Spectra were automatically obtained by UV-Probe system software. Glimepiride tablets were purchased from market, all the chemicals and reagents used were used of analytical grade.⁴

Solvent used

In the start of the method development for this drug, different solvents were tested such as water, methanol, 0.1N NaOH, Phosphate buffer and Acetonitrile.⁵

Method development

Preparation of standard stock solution

Standard stock solution of Glimepiride, having concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, was prepared in 0.1N NaOH. From these solutions, 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, Glimepiride respectively standard solution were prepared by dilution with 0.1N NaOH.⁶

Optical parameters

The optical parameters such as beer's law limit, molar extinction coefficients, % RSD were calculated. Regression characteristics like slope, intercept, correlation coefficient, LOD, LOQ standard were calculated.⁷

Selection of analytical wavelengths

Appropriate dilutions were prepared for drug from the standard stock 'B' solution and scanned in the spectrum mode from 200 nm to 400 nm. The absorption maximum was found at 228.4 for glimepiride.⁸

Preparation of calibration curve for Glimepiride

Appropriate volume of aliquots was pipette out from the standard stock solution in to a series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. The volume was made up to the mark with 0.1N NaOH to obtain concentrations of 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of AML. Absorbance of the above solutions were measured at 228 nm and a calibration curve of absorbance against concentration was plotted.⁹

Analysis of tablet formulation

Twenty tablets were weighed and their average weight was determined and finely powdered. The powder equivalent to 2 mg of GLIM was accurately weighed and transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in 50 ml 0.1N NaOH and the content was kept in Sonicator for 20 min. The flask was shaken and volume was made up to the mark with distilled water and made 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ stock solution, working standard solution of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration was prepares with appropriate dilutions. The absorbance of sample solutions were measured at 228.4 nm and their concentrations were determined using proposed analytical methods.¹⁰

Validation of spectrophotometric method

Linearity and Range

The linearity of analytical method is its ability to elicit test results that are directly proportional to the concentration of analyte in sample within a given range. The range of analytical method is the interval between the upper and lower levels of analyte that have been demonstrated to be determined within a suitable level of precision, accuracy and linearity.¹¹

Accuracy

To study the accuracy, 20 tablets were weighed and powdered and analysis of the same was carried out. To ascertain the accuracy of proposed methods, recovery studies were carried out by standard addition method at three different levels (80%, 100% and 120%).

Precision

Precision (intra-day precision) of the method was evaluated by carrying out the six independent test samples of the Glimepiride. The intermediate precision (inter-day precision) of the method was also evaluated using two different analyst, and different

days in the same laboratory. The percent relative standard deviation (%RSD) obtained was found to be good.¹²

Intra-day precision

Variation of results within the same day was analyzed. Intraday precision was determined by analyzing Glimepiride for three times in the same day at selected analytical wavelengths.

Inter-day precision

Variation of results between the days was analysed. Interday precision was determined by analyzing Glimepiride daily once for three days at selected analytical wavelengths.

Repeatability

Standard solutions of Glimepiride (3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18 µg/ml) were prepared and absorbance was measured at 228.4 nm and taking the 0.1N NaOH as the blank. The absorbance of the same concentration solution was measured six times and standard deviation was calculated.

Reproducibility

The absorbances were measured by another analyst and the values obtained were evaluated using t - test to verify their reproducibility.¹³

Linearity and Range

The linearity of analytical method is its ability to elicit test results that are directly proportional to the concentration of analyte in sample within a given range. The range of analytical method is the interval

between the upper and lower levels of analyte that have been demonstrated to be determined within a suitable level of precision, accuracy and linearity.

Limit of detection and limit of quantitation

Detection limit is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be detected, but not necessarily quantitated. The quantitation limit is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be determined with acceptable precision and accuracy under the stated experimental conditions. Detection limit and quantitation limit were determined based on the standard deviation of response and slope of calibration curve

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The absorbance of solution was measured at 228.4 nm for estimation of GLIM, respectively (Fig 1).The calibration curves were constructed by plotting absorbance versus concentration and the regression equation were generated (Figure 2)

Validation of the method

Results of validation studies are summarized in Table 1. The accuracy of the method was confirmed by recovery studies from tablet at 80%, 100% and 120% levels of standard addition and the results are depicted in Table 2. Recovery in the range of 100-101% justifies the accuracy of the method.

Analysis of Marketed Formulation The method was applied to marketed tablet (AMRYL) containing GLIM 2 mg. Results shows that this method can be successfully applied to marketed formulations.¹⁴

Figure 2 Overlain Spectra of Glimepiride at 228.4 nm

Figure 3 Calibration curve for Glimepiride at 228.4 nm

Table 1 Optical parameters

Parameter	Result
Absorption maxima	249 nm
Linearity range	5-30 µg/ml
Standard regression equation	0.01704x+0.004133
Correlation coefficient	0.999732
Molar absorptivity	8491
Standard deviation	0.159437
LOD (µg/ml)	0.4
LOQ (µg/ml)	1.2
Standard deviation	0.002
%RSD	0.772

CONCLUSION:

Proposed study describes method for the estimation of GLIM. The method was validated and found to be simple, sensitive, accurate and precise as per ICH guidelines. The method was successfully used for determination of drugs in their pharmaceutical formulation.

Acknowledgments

The authors are thankful to USV Pharmaceutical Ltd. Mumbai, India for providing gift sample of Glimepiride. The authors are very thankful to Principal and Management of SSRCP College for providing necessary facilities to carry out research work.

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